

Health information distribution to Deaf people in the Western Cape and the involved stakeholders

Four conceptual models of health information distributions to Deaf people in Western Cape were developed based on the data retrieved from Co-exploration activity 1. The first three conceptual models were constructed from perspectives of the key informants, groups of Deaf participants, and all health professionals, respectively.

Health information distribution based on the key informants' perspective

From the key informants' perspective, DOHWC is in charge of scheduling health programs, allocating funds, and mandating health services and information delivered through health professionals to all patients. It tries to ensure that Deaf people would have health information access similar to other populations in the province. A responsible department of DOHWC, therefore, approaches Deaf-run organizations to promote health information.

DCCT is one of the Deaf-run organizations which collaborates with DOHWC to distribute health information to their members. DCCT offers a wide range of programs to uplift Deaf people in multiple aspects, for all genders and all age groups. At the time, there were 15 programs regarding social developments and one program for HIV/AIDS counseling. These programs were launched based on the interests among the Deaf members and the available funding. HIV/AIDS lay counseling for Deaf people is a prioritized program that others are run in parallel. Information about HIV/AIDS, its comorbid disease, like tuberculosis (TB), and Sexual Transmitted Diseases (STDs) is delivered to Deaf people through the HIV/AIDS counseling program. The program sometimes covers information on other diseases when common health misconceptions are detected among Deaf people, such as the misconceptions regarding prostate cancer. There are two kinds of services in the HIV/AIDS counseling program, which are individual counseling and health workshops. The first operates within Cape Town and its vicinity. The latter serves clusters of Deaf people in Cape Town and rural areas across Western Cape: Khayelitsha,

Vredenburg, Paarl, Beaufort West, George, and Robertson. The HIV/AIDS counseling program was, at that time, supervised by a hearing social worker (one of the key informants in this interview) and executed together with four Deaf health workers. These Deaf health workers were funded for their training and accredited by DOHWC to work as part of the healthcare services. This team has been collaborating with Aids Training, Information, and Counseling Center (ATICC).

DCCT members, as well, received health information on specific diseases delivered via SMS from a pilot program of HHRP. The information was written in simple English to be Deaf-friendly. If the Deaf members could not understand some of the messages, they would ask DCCT staff for clarification.

From the perspective of the key informants, DOHWC, HHRP, Deaf health workers of DCCT, hearing health professionals, and Deaf peers were stated as the main stakeholders involved in the distributions of health information to Deaf people. These insights unveil the paths that health information reaches DCCT members, including other Deaf communities across Western Cape (see Figure 1). The arrows pointing to the right refer to the direction in which health information reaches a Deaf person. The arrows pointing to the direction opposite the first ones convey the Deaf person's interaction with the information source to inquire clarifications on the health information. The arrows with dashed lines denote the interactions obstructed by the language barrier.

Figure 1. Health information distributed to Deaf people according to the key informants.

Next, the identification from Deaf participants' perspective is provided.

Health information distribution based on the Deaf participants' perspective

The identification of the stakeholders from the Deaf participants' perspective was retrieved from the interviews with the Deaf-men group, the Deaf-women group, and three Deaf families with at least a CODA. The responses from the CODAs were excluded from this part of the analysis. The Deaf participants from all groups mentioned 14 sources which they currently seek or receive health information. Figure 2 presents these health information sources. They were ranked according to the frequency that individual Deaf participants mentioned them. The list implies the stakeholders involved in the health information delivery for Deaf people.

The list of the current health information sources
Ranking (Based on the count of mentions among the participants
of all Deaf groups)

Ranking	number of mentions
1	9
1	9
2	5
3	3
3	3
4	2
4	1
5	1
	1
	1
	1
5	1
	1
	1
	1

Figure 2. Current health information sources of Deaf people.

Besides this identification, the Deaf participants' feedback on each health information source was unveiled. The findings as follows were published in a journal paper ([Chininthron, Glaser, Tucker, and Diehl, 2016](#)).

A consultation with a health professional in the absence of a SASLI was one of the most frequently mentioned information sources (nine mentions). The Deaf participants visited a primary health center in their area to receive free-of-charge health services when falling sick. They addressed that the health information delivered through such consultation is inaccessible because of the language barrier. Without the SASLI, a Deaf patient and a health professional had to communicate via writing and reading or lip-reading, which not all Deaf people are good at. A participant from the Deaf-women group expressed that

she could not focus on the written messages when the piece of paper was passed back and forth. All participants from the Deaf-men group revealed that they took the paper home, but no friends or family members could interpret the messages for them. This situation was common among Deaf people who lived with family members who could not communicate in SASL. As opposed to the response from the Deaf-men group, the participants from the Deaf-family groups discussed that their CODA always helped interpret the written messages. Participants from the Deaf-women group additionally revealed that many Deaf patients pretended to understand explanations during health consultation by head nodding to avoid emotional conflicts with their health professional: *“when it comes to writing back and forth with the doctor, it’s difficult to deal with. You will say (nod) yes, yes, yes to everything. And then when you go outside, you will ask people what it means because when you stop them (doctors), they get furious”* (Chininthorn et al., 2016, p. 7).

The lay counseling and workshop provided by DCCT was another source with the highest ranking (nine mentions). A participant from the Deaf-women group mentioned that she occasionally received an invitation via SMS from DCCT to attend a monthly gathering with a health workshop. The participants of all Deaf groups stated that they could very well understand the health information in SASL delivered during DCCT’s health program. A participant of a Deaf-family group stated: *“the drama from DCCT is very good. It clarifies the doubts I used to have. The drama is the must-see for Deaf people.”* Besides positive feedback, several Deaf participants gave some remarks on the drama. Since this health drama was a live performance and performed at a specific place, the Deaf audiences must travel to the venue to watch it. The Deaf participants gave a mutual remark that they did not always have sufficient budget for transportation. The participants from two Deaf-family groups expected that DCCT would come up with an intervention that would allow them to access or review health dramas or health information at their convenience. Some participants in the Deaf-female group added that fewer jokes should be performed in the health drama, so the audience would not be distracted from the core message.

The Deaf participants from multiple groups stated that printed media were their sources of health information. Newspaper ranked the second place (five mentions) based on the mentions of the Deaf participants across all groups.

Pamphlets from health facilities earned the fifth place (one mention). A participant from the Deaf-women group often took pamphlets distributed during a support group for self-studies. This was because she could not understand health information delivered during a support group which conducted by a hearing health professional for mostly hearing patients. This participant addressed that pamphlets with pictures and concise texts were accessible for Deaf people. Magazine co-ranked the fifth place (one mention); a participant from the Deaf-family group discussed that she regularly received information concerning her chronic disease from her favorite magazine. Although these Deaf participants did not understand the terminology used in articles, they could construct their understanding from the understood wording in combination with the accompanying pictures.

Parents of the Deaf participants co-ranked the third place (three mentions). Two participants from Deaf-family groups received some health information from their mother; however, the information was limited due to the language barrier. Except for one participant from the Deaf-men groups regularly received health information from his Deaf mother working at DCCT. Many Deaf participants could not learn health information from their parents because of the language barrier; the parents had not had SASL skills.

Deaf friends co-ranked the third place (three mentions) because the Deaf participants could reach this kind of information source at any time. Deaf friends who had better reading skills than other peers could read and explain medication instructions. Some of the respected Deaf friends could advise some home remedies or suggest a contact of Deaf-friendly staff at a health facility.

Hearing friends received the fourth place (two mentions) based on the responses from one participant of the Deaf-male group and one participant of the Deaf-female group. Somehow, these participants experienced a language barrier while communicating with hearing friends. Through the disrupted communication, one of these participants developed some health misconceptions that affect his self-caring. The misunderstanding that *"Smoking is good for your health. It's good for your brain. It gives you ideas"* motivated the participant to smoke. After long-term smoking, he discovered that the benefits of smoking were untrue. The same participant shared further

on his use of a dangerous substance to heal abnormal discharge from his penis. A hearing friend suggested him drinking water diluted with insect repellent fluid to cured the symptom; he tried it and found the symptoms disappear.

The rest of the stated stakeholders earned one mention each. They co-ranked in the fifth place. Events held by DeafSA were mentioned by a participant from the Deaf-women group as her health information source. The information presented during the events was in SASL, and it was accessible for her. Traditional healers were considered by a participant of the Deaf-men group considered as one of his health information sources. However, he stated that his communication with the healers was baffling. Health education at school during his childhood was mentioned by a participant from the Deaf-men group; he defined this information source lay fundamental health knowledge for him. The Internet was indicated by a participant from the Deaf-women group as an indirect source that leads its users to direct information health information sources. The participant frequently browsed the Internet for definitions of the terminologies she was in doubt. Unfortunately, many Deaf people had not had access to the Internet. TV program without SASL interpreting was mentioned by a participant from a Deaf-family group. The participant considered her favorite TV program, Dr. Oz, as one of her health information sources. However, no SASL interpretation was rendered for this TV program. Such information source, therefore, required this participant to lip-read and construct her understanding in combination with the visuals appearing during the show. This participant elaborated further that she usually asked her CODA to interpret complicated health topics during the show. SMSes and presentations from HHRP were stated by a Deaf participant of the Deaf-women group. The text messages were written in simple English, isiXhosa, or Afrikaans, which many Deaf people could understand. Even though some participants from the same group argued that they could not fully understand the message, they still agreed that receiving such information was better than receiving nothing.

Interestingly, none of the Deaf parents considered their CODA as their health information source. CODAs played an important role in conveying health information from the original information sources to their Deaf parents. Two out of five CODAs, especially the firstborn of the Deaf families in these focus

groups, took responsibility to escort each of their Deaf parents to a health consultation and interpret the communication between the parent and health professionals. In addition, they continuously shared health information learned in school, newspaper, radio, or TV programs with their Deaf parents.

The paths that health information reaches Deaf people according to the Deaf participants are presented in Figure 3. Several stakeholders who had delivered health information to Deaf people were identified similarly to what the key informants stated (Figure 1). The differences were that the Deaf participants did not know of DOHWC, and they identified an extensive list of information sources which they optionally sought and received health information from. The directions of the arrows and the dashed lines carry the same meaning as described beforehand.

Figure 3. Health information distributed to Deaf people according to the Deaf participants.

HHRP, Deaf health workers of DCCT, and the hearing health professionals are the stakeholders who deliver health information to Deaf people Western Cape as identified by the key informants and the Deaf participants. Thereafter, these entities were invited to join the co-exploration stage. The HHRP members declined the invitation because they did not consider their organization as a health information source for the Deaf people. The health-related SMSes which the Deaf people received were their research tools, not the actual health information distribution. Thus, they referred the author to the health policymakers who had been involving in health information delivery to Deaf people and the health professionals who had had experiences

in serving Deaf people. The findings from the interviews with these health professionals are in the next sub-section.

In summary, DCCT Deaf health workers, DOHWC health policymakers, hearing health professionals working at a primary health center were interviewed.

Health information distribution based on the health professionals' perspective

All health professionals were asked to identify the stakeholders who are involved in the health information distributed to Deaf people in Western Cape by using the influence map to rate the influence of each stakeholder on Deaf people's health and well-being.

The Deaf health workers explained that Deaf patients from their casework mostly received and sought health information from DCCT. Therefore, DCCT earned the first place in influencing the health and well-being of many Deaf people. Deaf people also indirectly received health information from the medical SASLIs during their escorts to health facilities. As such the medical SASLIs co-ranked the first place. HHRP provided these medical SASLIs at no-charge for the Deaf patients who made a booking. As such, this organization received the second place in the ranking. DOHWC received the third place because they were the one who assigned and funds health programs that were Deaf-inclusive. Health facilities, which were hospitals and primary health centers, received the fourth place because Deaf patients received treatments regardless of in/inaccessible health information. The Deaf health workers' view of health information distribution to Deaf people was similar to the key informants'. The difference was that the Deaf health workers did not consider Deaf peers as a health information source of Deaf people.

The ranking that the health policymakers rated differed from the Deaf health workers'. DeafSA received the first place because it networks with Deaf communities within Cape Town and Western Cape. Therefore, it could affect health and well-being among Deaf people. The second place was given to DOH and DOHWC who mandated health programs at both national and provincial levels. Various Deaf schools received the third and the fourth place in the ranking because a couple of schools could provide both health services and health information on site, while many other schools only provided health

education for their learners. The supporting health organizations, such as Diabetes SA, Unambo, Epilepsy SA, and ComCare received the fifth-ranking for their operations that supported health services in Western Cape. However, these organizations did not mainly serve Deaf people. Parliament and governments received the sixth place for their inclusive-healthcare law enforcement. Interestingly, these health policymakers were unaware of the existence of the Deaf workers at DCCT.

As opposed to other health professionals, the hearing health professionals from a primary health center did not know other health information sources which their Deaf patients may approach. Nevertheless, their services were considered as a health information source for the Deaf patients.

Figure 4 summarizes health information distribution to Deaf people from the perspective of the Deaf and hearing health professionals. It differs from Figures 3 and 1 because it includes organizations in different levels of health promotions, ranged from the parliament to individual health professionals. The organizations which do not especially serve Deaf people are also appended in the figure.

Figure 4. Health information distributed to Deaf people according to the Deaf and hearing health professionals.

Summary of the stakeholders

Health information in South Africa has been standardized by the central DOH that has been cooperating with DOHWC in mandating and scheduling health programs and promotions of health at the national and provincial levels. DOHWC has been partnering with health facilities and Deaf communities to deliver health information to the Deaf population. These organizations have been stakeholders who Deaf people frequently seek and receive health services and information. DCCT is a Deaf organization with health workers who are Deaf. Their Deaf health workers deliver health information HIV/AIDS specifically to the Deaf people across Western Cape. These Deaf health workers promote health information during health a workshop to a big group of Deaf people and one-to-one lay counseling for an individual Deaf patient. They do not have language barriers when communicating with Deaf people. Hearing health professionals at primary health centers are involved in the health services and information delivered to Deaf people who fall sick and visit the health facilities for treatments. The health professionals at a primary health center majorly deliver health services and information through face-to-face consultations with individual patients, including the Deaf patients. However, they often struggled to communicate with their Deaf patients when there was no SASLI.

Figure 5 summarizes this distribution of health information to Deaf people.

Figure 5. The paths of health information distributed to Deaf people through the commonly stated stakeholders in Cape Town and Western Cape.

References

Chininthorn, P., Glaser, M., Tucker, W.D., & Diehl, J.C. (2016). Exploration of Deaf people's health information sources and techniques for information delivery in Cape Town: A qualitative study for the

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